

A VARIANT OF NIM PLAYED ON BOOLEAN MATRICES

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Abstract

We introduce a version of Nim played on a Boolean matrix. Each player, in turn, removes a nonzero row or column. The last player to remove a row or column wins. We investigate the Boolean matrices that represent the Ferrers diagram of an integer partition. An integer partition in which each summand is greater than the number of terms in the partition is said to be strong. The Grundy numbers of Boolean matrices that represent the Ferrers diagram of any integer partition consisting of three or fewer terms are determined. This allows us to classify the \mathcal{P} -positions and \mathcal{N} -positions of Boolean matrices that represent the Ferrers diagram of any strong integer partition.

1. Introduction

Combinatorial game theory (CGT) developed in the context of recreational mathematics. In their seminal work and with a spirit of playfulness, Berlekamp, Conway and Guy [3, 6] established the mathematical framework from which games of complete information could be studied. The power of this theory would soon become apparent and was utilized by many researchers (see Fraenkel's bibliography [8]). Along with its natural appeal, combinatorial game theory has applications

in complexity theory, logic and biology. Literature on the subject continues to increase and the interested reader can find comprehensive introductions to CGT in [2, 3, 6, 14]. Additional research articles with a theoretical flavor can be found in [1, 10, 11, 12, 13].

We first recall some basic concepts from CGT which are used in this paper. Terms which are not explicitly defined can be found in [14]. A *combinatorial game* is one of complete information and no element of chance is involved in gameplay. Each player is aware of the game position at any point in the game. Under *normal play*, two players (Player 1 and Player 2) alternate taking turns and a player loses when he cannot make a move. An *impartial* combinatorial game is one where both players have the same options from any position. A *finite* game eventually terminates (with a winner and a loser, no draws allowed). It is understood that Player 1 makes the first move in any combinatorial game.

For any finite impartial combinatorial game Γ , there is an associated nonnegative integer value $\text{Gr}(\Gamma)$. This value immediately tells us if Γ is a \mathcal{P} -*position* (previous player win) or an \mathcal{N} -*position* (next player win). In particular, $\text{Gr}(\Gamma) = 0$ if and only if Γ is a \mathcal{P} -position. To compute $\text{Gr}(\Gamma)$, we need the following definitions.

The *minimum excluded value* (or *mex*) of a multiset of nonnegative integers is the smallest nonnegative integer which does not appear in the multiset. This is denoted by $\text{mex}\{t_1, t_2, t_3, \dots, t_k\}$. Let Γ be a finite impartial game. Then, the *Grundy number* (or *Grundy-value*) of Γ is defined to be

$$\text{Gr}(\Gamma) = \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(\Delta) : \Delta \text{ is an option of } \Gamma\}.$$

The *sum* of finite impartial games is the game obtained by placing the individual games, side by side. On a player's turn, a move is made in a single summand. Under normal play, the last person to make a move wins. For any finite impartial game $\Gamma = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 + \dots + \gamma_k$, the Grundy number of Γ is computed in the following way. First, convert $\text{Gr}(\gamma_i)$ into binary. Then, compute $\bigoplus \text{Gr}(\gamma_i)$, where the sum is BitXor (Nim-addition). Finally, convert this value back into a nonnegative integer.

Nim is a short impartial combinatorial game, which is played in the following manner:

- There are n heaps, each containing a finite number of stones. Two players alternate turns, each time choosing a heap and removing any number (≥ 1) of stones in that heap. The player who cannot make a move loses the game.

In 1902, Bouton [5] gave a beautiful mathematical analysis and complete solution for Nim. Since then, the game of Nim and its variants have been the subject of many CGT research papers. Within the literature, studies on Nim variants with modified rule sets, Nim played on different configurations (circular, triangular and rectangular), and Nim played on graphs can be found. Variants of Nim played on Boolean matrices were analyzed in [4, 7, 9].

2. A Matrix Game

In this paper, we introduce and analyze yet another variant of Nim played on a Boolean matrix. A matrix M of zeros and ones is chosen. A *line* of the matrix is either a row or a column. A line is *nonzero* if some entry in the line is not zero. Two players alternate turns. At each turn, a player selects a nonzero line and removes that line from the matrix. The player who makes the last move wins.

Is there a general strategy that can force a win for the first player for a reasonable collection of matrices?

Remark 1. We note that a line which has all zeros has no effect on the game and can be deleted. Whenever a line consists entirely of zeros after a player’s move, we will remove all lines consisting entirely of zeros without affecting the outcome of the game.

Remark 2. Given a matrix game A , any permutation of rows of A and any permutation of columns of A yield games that are equivalent to A . Also, the transpose A^T is equivalent to A .

Our first result applies to permutation matrices.

Proposition 1. *Let P_n be any $n \times n$ permutation matrix. Then,*

- $\text{Gr}(P_n) = 0$ whenever n is even and
- $\text{Gr}(P_n) = 1$ whenever n is odd.

Proof. By Remark 2, any permutation matrix P_n is equivalent to the the $n \times n$ identity matrix I_n . We observe that $\text{Gr}(I_0) = 0$. We apply induction on n . Since every row and column of I_n has exactly one entry with a value of 1, removing any column or row will leave a corresponding column or row consisting entirely of zeros. By Remark 1, we may remove this column or row consisting entirely of zeros. Thus, every allowable move results in the $(n - 1) \times (n - 1)$ identity matrix I_{n-1} . If n is odd, then $\text{Gr}(I_n) = \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(I_{n-1})\} = \text{mex}\{0\} = 1$. If n is even, then $\text{Gr}(I_n) = \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(I_{n-1})\} = \text{mex}\{1\} = 0$. □

Let $J_{m,n}$ denote the $m \times n$ matrix with every entry 1. Observe that there are at most two moves from $J_{m,n}$, up to isomorphism, these being $J_{m,n} \rightarrow J_{m-1,n}$ or $J_{m,n} \rightarrow J_{m,n-1}$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) \leq 2$. We take $J_{0,k}$ and $J_{k,0}$ to denote the game with the 0×0 matrix. Since there are no moves possible from this game, $\text{Gr}(J_{0,k}) = \text{Gr}(J_{k,0}) = 0$.

Theorem 1. *Suppose that $m, n \geq 1$.*

- *If $1 \in \{m, n\}$ and $m + n$ is odd, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 2$.*

- If $1 \in \{m, n\}$ and $m + n$ is even, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 1$.
- If $2 \in \{m, n\}$ and $m + n$ is odd, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 2$.
- If $m, n \geq 2$ and $m + n$ is even, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 0$.
- If $m, n \geq 3$ and $m + n$ is odd, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 1$.

Proof. By Remark 2, the games $J_{m,n}$ and $J_{n,m}$ are equivalent. Thus, we may assume that $m \leq n$.

For $m = 1$, the only possible moves are $J_{1,n} \rightarrow J_{0,0}$ and $J_{1,n} \rightarrow J_{1,n-1}$. We observe that $\text{Gr}(J_{1,1}) = \text{mex}\{0\} = 1$ and $\text{Gr}(J_{1,2}) = \text{mex}\{1, 0\} = 2$. By induction on $k \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Gr}(J_{1,2k+1}) &= \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(J_{1,2k}), 0\} = \text{mex}\{2, 0\} = 1, \text{ and} \\ \text{Gr}(J_{1,2k+2}) &= \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(J_{1,2k+1}), 0\} = \text{mex}\{1, 0\} = 2. \end{aligned}$$

For $m = 2$ and $n \geq 1$, the possible moves are $J_{2,n} \rightarrow J_{1,n}$ and $J_{2,n} \rightarrow J_{1,n-1}$. Since $\text{Gr}(J_{2,1}) = 2$ and $\text{Gr}(J_{2,2}) = \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(J_{2,1}), \text{Gr}(J_{1,2})\} = \text{mex}\{2, 2\} = 0$, we have, by induction on $k \geq 1$,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Gr}(J_{2,2k+1}) &= \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(J_{2,2k}), \text{Gr}(J_{1,2k+1})\} = \text{mex}\{0, 1\} = 2, \text{ and} \\ \text{Gr}(J_{2,2k+2}) &= \text{mex}\{\text{Gr}(J_{2,2k+1}), \text{Gr}(J_{1,2k+2})\} = \text{mex}\{2, 2\} = 0. \end{aligned}$$

For $n \geq m \geq 3$, we proceed by induction on $k = m + n$. If k is odd, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m-1,n}) = 0$, and $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n-1}) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 1$. If k is even, then $\text{Gr}(J_{m-1,n}) \in \{2, 1\}$, and $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n-1}) \in \{2, 1\}$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(J_{m,n}) = 0$. This completes the proof. \square

Let U_n denote the upper triangular $n \times n$ matrix whose (i, j) entry is 1 if $i \leq j$ and 0 if $i > j$. A computer program yields the following calculations: $\text{Gr}(U_n) = 1$ for $n = 1, 3, 5$, $\text{Gr}(U_n) = 2$ for $n = 7, 9$, and $\text{Gr}(U_n) = 0$ for $n = 2, 4, 6, 8, 10$.

Conjecture 1. For any even integer $n \geq 2$, $\text{Gr}(U_n) = 0$.

We now introduce some notation for games that arise from U_n . After deleting some lines, the resulting matrix will have at least as many ones in row i as in row $i + 1$, and at least as many ones in column $i + 1$ as in column i . Also, each row has its ones in the last positions of the row, and each column has its ones in the first positions of the column. Thus, the position can be described by a vector $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$, where row i has a_i ones, in the last a_i positions of row i . We use λ for the null string, and $[\lambda]$ for the lone partition of zero (the list with no elements). If $\pi = [a_1, \dots, a_k]$ and $\rho = [a'_1, \dots, a'_j]$ is a position that can be reached from π in a single move, we write $\pi \rightarrow \rho$.

Definition 1. Let M be an $m \times n$ matrix whose entries are 0's and 1's. The *game weight* of M , denoted by $\text{wt}(M)$, is the number of entries of M that have value 1.

Definition 2. Given $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$, the *length* of A , denoted by $\text{len}(A)$, is the number of terms in the sequence (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) . Thus, $\text{len}(A) = k$.

Observe that $[a_1]$ is the $1 \times a_1$ matrix of all ones.

Corollary 1. *Suppose $a_1 \geq 1$.*

- *If a_1 is odd, then $\text{Gr}([a_1]) = 1$.*
- *If a_1 is even, then $\text{Gr}([a_1]) = 2$.*

Proof. By Theorem 1, $\text{Gr}([a_1]) = \text{Gr}(J_{1,a_1}) = 1$ if a_1 is odd, and $\text{Gr}([a_1]) = \text{Gr}(J_{1,a_1}) = 2$ if a_1 is even. □

3. Grundy Numbers of $[a_1, a_2]$

We determine the Grundy number of $[a_1, a_2]$ for all $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq 1$.

Theorem 2. *Suppose $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq 1$.*

- *If a_1 is even, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = 0$.*
- *If either a_1 and a_2 are both odd with $a_2 > 1$, or $a_1 = a_2 = 1$, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = 2$.*
- *If $a_1 > 1$ is odd and either a_2 is even or 1, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = 3$.*

Proof. By Theorem 1, $\text{Gr}([1, 1]) = \text{Gr}(J_{2,1}) = 2$. The proof will be by induction on the game weight $\text{wt}([a_1, a_2]) = a_1 + a_2$ of $[a_1, a_2]$.

Case 1. Assume a_1 is even and $a_2 = 1$. If a column of $[a_1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1]$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1]) = 2$ if $a_1 = 2$ and $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1]) = 3$ if $a_1 \geq 4$. Also, by Corollary 1, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1]) = 1$.

If a row of $[a_1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1]$ and $[1]$. By Corollary 1, $\text{Gr}([a_1]) = 2$ and $\text{Gr}([1]) = 1$. Thus, if $a_1 = 2$,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, 1]) = \text{mex}\{1, 2\} = 0,$$

and if $a_1 \geq 4$,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, 1]) = \text{mex}\{1, 2, 3\} = 0.$$

Case 2. Assume $a_1 > 1$ is odd and $a_2 = 1$. If a column of $[a_1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1]$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1]) = 0$, and by Corollary 1, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1]) = 2$.

If a row of $[a_1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1]$ and $[1]$. By Corollary 1, $\text{Gr}([a_1]) = 1$ and $\text{Gr}([1]) = 1$. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, 1]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 2\} = 3.$$

Case 3. Assume a_1 is even and $a_2 > 1$ is odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 2 and 3, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1]$ and $[a_2]$ which have Grundy numbers 2 and 1, respectively, by Corollary 1. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = \text{mex}\{1, 2, 3\} = 0.$$

Case 4. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$. We observe that $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, a_2]) = 3$ by the inductive hypothesis. Also, if either $a_1 = a_2 = 2$ or $a_2 \geq 4$, then $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]) = 2$; otherwise, if $a_1 \geq 4$ and $a_2 = 2$, then $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]) = 3$. If a row of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1]$ and $[a_2]$ which both have Grundy number 2 by Corollary 1. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = \text{mex}\{2, 3\} = 0.$$

Case 5. Assume both a_1 and $a_2 > 1$ are odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ which both have Grundy number 0 by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1]$ and $[a_2]$ which both have Grundy number 1 by Corollary 1. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1\} = 2.$$

Case 6. Assume a_1 is odd and a_2 is even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ which both have Grundy number 0 by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1]$ and $[a_2]$ which have Grundy numbers 1 and 2, respectively, by Corollary 1. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 2\} = 3.$$

□

4. Grundy Numbers of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$

For the game $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$, there are effectively only six possible moves: delete one of the three rows, or delete a column with one, two or three ones in it. Hence, the Grundy number of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is at most 6.

Theorem 3. *Suppose $a_1 \geq 1$. Then,*

- $\text{Gr}([1, 1, 1]) = 1$,
- $\text{Gr}([a_1, 1, 1]) = 0$ if $a_1 > 1$ is odd, and
- $\text{Gr}([a_1, 1, 1]) = 3$ if a_1 is even.

Proof. Since $[1, 1, 1]$ is isomorphic to $[3]$, we have $\text{Gr}([1, 1, 1]) = \text{Gr}([3]) = 1$ by Corollary 1. We induct on a_1 .

Case 1. Assume a_1 is even. If a column of $[a_1, 1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1]$. We have $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1, 1]) = 1$ for $a_2 = 2$, and $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1, 1]) = 0$ for $a_2 > 2$ by the inductive hypothesis. By Corollary 1, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1]) = 1$.

If a row of $[a_1, 1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, 1]$ and $[1, 1]$. By Theorem 2, $\text{Gr}([a_1, 1]) = 0$ and $\text{Gr}([1, 1]) = 2$. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 2\} = 3.$$

Case 2. Assume $a_1 > 1$ is odd. If a column of $[a_1, 1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1]$. We have $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1, 1]) = 3$ by the inductive hypothesis, and $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1]) = 2$ by Corollary 1.

If a row of $[a_1, 1, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, 1]$ and $[1, 1]$. By Theorem 2, $\text{Gr}([a_1, 1]) = 3$ and $\text{Gr}([1, 1]) = 2$. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = \text{mex}\{2, 3\} = 0.$$

□

Theorem 4. *Suppose a_1 and a_2 are integers such that $a_1 \geq a_2 > 1$.*

- *If a_1 is odd, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = 1$.*
- *If a_1 is even with $a_1 \geq 4$ and either a_2 is odd or $a_2 = 2$, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = 2$.*
- *If a_1 and a_2 are both even with $a_2 \geq 4$, or $a_1 = a_2 = 2$, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = 3$.*

Proof. The proof is by induction on the game weight of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$. We prove the result assuming $a_1 > a_2$. We leave the proof of the case $a_1 = a_2$ to the reader.

Case 1. Assume a_1 is even with $a_1 \geq 4$ and $a_2 = 2$. If a column of $[a_1, 2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, 2, 1]$, $[a_1 - 1, 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1, 1]$. We have $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 2, 1]) = 1$ by the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1, 1]) = 0$ by Theorem 3, and $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, 1]) = 3$ by Theorem 2. If a row of $[a_1, 2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, 2]$, $[a_1, 1]$, and $[2, 1]$ which all have Grundy number 0 by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 3\} = 2.$$

Case 2. Assume a_1 and a_2 are odd with $a_2 \geq 3$. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 1]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 2 by the inductive hypothesis, 2 if $a_2 = 3$ or 3 if $a_2 > 3$ by the inductive hypothesis, and 0 by Theorem 2, respectively. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 1]$, and $[a_2, 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 2, 3, and 3, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = \text{mex}\{0, 2, 3\} = 1.$$

Case 3. Assume a_1 is odd and a_2 is even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 1]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$. The Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 1]$ is 2 if $a_1 \geq 5$ and $a_2 = 2$ by the inductive hypothesis, or 3 if $a_2 \geq 4$ by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ is 3 if $a_1 \geq 5$ and $a_2 = 2$ by Theorem 3, or 2 if $a_2 \geq 4$ by the inductive hypothesis. In addition, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ is 0 by Theorem 2. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 1]$, and $[a_2, 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 3, 3, and 0, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = \text{mex}\{0, 2, 3\} = 1.$$

Case 4. Assume a_1 is even and a_2 is odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 1]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 1, 1, and 3, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis and Theorem 2. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 1]$, and $[a_2, 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 0, 0, and 3, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 3\} = 2.$$

Case 5. Assume a_1 and a_2 are both even with $a_2 \geq 4$. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 1]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 1, 1, and 2, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis

and Theorem 2. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 1]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 1]$, and $[a_2, 1]$ which all have Grundy number 0 by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 1]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 2\} = 3.$$

□

Theorem 5. *Suppose a_1 and a_2 are integers such that $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq 2$.*

- *If a_1 and a_2 are both odd, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = 0$.*
- *If a_1 is odd and a_2 is even, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = 1$.*
- *If a_1 is even, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = 2$.*

Proof. The proof is by induction on the game weight of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$. We prove the result assuming $a_1 > a_2$. We leave the proof of the case $a_1 = a_2$ to the reader.

Case 1. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$, and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$. The Grundy numbers of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$ are each 2 by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ is 2 if $a_1 \geq 5$ and $a_2 = 3$, or 3 if $a_2 \geq 5$ by Theorem 4. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 2]$, and $[a_2, 2]$ which have Grundy numbers 2, 3, and 3, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = \text{mex}\{2, 3\} = 0.$$

Case 2. Assume a_1 is odd and a_2 is even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$, and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$. The Grundy numbers of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$ are each 2 by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ is 3 if $a_2 = 2$ by Theorem 3, or 2 if $a_2 \geq 4$ by Theorem 4. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 2]$, and $[a_2, 2]$ which have Grundy numbers 3, 3, and 0, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = \text{mex}\{0, 2, 3\} = 1.$$

Case 3. Assume a_1 is even and a_2 is odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$, and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ which have Grundy numbers 0, 1, and 1, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis and Theorem 4. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 2]$, and $[a_2, 2]$ which have Grundy numbers 0, 0, and 3, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 3\} = 2.$$

Case 4. Assume a_1 and a_2 are both even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$, and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$. The Grundy numbers of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 2]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$ are 1 and 0, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 1]$ is 0 if $a_2 = 2$ by Theorem 3, or 1 if $a_2 \geq 4$ by Theorem 4. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 2]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 2]$, and $[a_2, 2]$ which each have Grundy number 0 by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 2]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1\} = 2.$$

□

Theorem 6. *Suppose $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq 3$.*

- *If both a_1 and a_2 are odd, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = 0$.*
- *If both a_1 and a_2 are even, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 3]) = 1$.*
- *If a_1 is even and $a_3 > 3$, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = 1$.*
- *If a_1 is odd, a_2 is even, and a_3 is even, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = 2$.*
- *If a_1 is even and a_2 is odd, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 3]) = 3$.*
- *If a_1 is odd, a_2 is even, and a_3 is odd, then $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = 4$.*

Proof. The proof is by induction on the game weight of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$. We prove the result assuming $a_1 > a_2 > a_3$. We leave the proof of the cases when either $a_1 = a_2$ or $a_2 = a_3$ to the reader.

Case 1. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$. The Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$ is 3 if $a_3 = 3$ or 1 if $a_3 > 3$ by the inductive hypothesis. Similarly, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ is 1 by the inductive hypothesis, and the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$ is 2 if $a_3 = 3$ by Theorem 5 or 1 if $a_3 > 3$ by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, a_3]$, and $[a_2, a_3]$. We have $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2]) = 2$, and $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_3]) = \text{Gr}([a_2, a_3]) = 2$ if a_3 is odd or $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_3]) = \text{Gr}([a_2, a_3]) = 3$ if a_3 is even by Theorem 2. When $a_3 = 3$ or a_3 is even,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{1, 2, 3\} = 0,$$

and when a_3 is odd,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{1, 2\} = 0.$$

Case 2. Assume a_1 and a_2 are both even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$

which have Grundy numbers 2 if a_3 is even or 4 if a_3 is odd, 0, and 0, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis and Theorem 5. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, a_3]$, and $[a_2, a_3]$ which each have Grundy number 0 by Theorem 2. When a_3 is even,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 2\} = 1,$$

and when a_3 is odd,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 4\} = 1.$$

Case 3. Assume a_1 is even, a_2 is odd, and $a_3 > 3$. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$. The Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$ is 0 by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ is 2 if a_3 is even or 4 if a_3 is odd by the inductive hypothesis. Similarly, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$ is 4 if a_3 is even or 2 if a_3 is odd by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, a_3]$, and $[a_2, a_3]$ which have Grundy numbers 0, 0, and 3 if a_3 is even or 2 if a_3 is odd, respectively, by Theorem 2. When a_3 is even,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 2, 3, 4\} = 1,$$

and when $a_3 > 3$ is odd,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 2, 4\} = 1.$$

Case 4. Assume a_1 is odd, a_2 is even, and a_3 is even. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$. The Grundy numbers of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ are each 1 by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$ is 3 if $a_3 = 4$ or 1 if $a_3 > 4$ by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, a_3]$, and $[a_2, a_3]$ which have Grundy numbers 3, 3, and 0, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 3\} = 2.$$

Case 5. Assume a_1 is even, a_2 is odd, and $a_3 = 3$. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, 3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, 3]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, 2]$ which have Grundy numbers 0, 4, and 1, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis and Theorem 5. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, 3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, 3]$, and $[a_2, 3]$ which have Grundy numbers 0, 0, and 2, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, 3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 2, 4\} = 3.$$

Case 6. Assume a_1 is odd, a_2 is even, and a_3 is odd. If a column of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$, $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$. The Grundy numbers of $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3]$ and $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3]$ are 1 and 3 if $a_3 = 3$ or 1 if $a_3 > 3$, respectively, by the inductive hypothesis. Also, the Grundy number of $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3 - 1]$ is 2 if $a_3 = 3$ by Theorem 5 or 1 if $a_3 > 3$ by the inductive hypothesis. If a row of $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ is removed, the allowable positions are $[a_1, a_2]$, $[a_1, a_3]$, and $[a_2, a_3]$ which have Grundy numbers 3, 2, and 0, respectively, by Theorem 2. Thus,

$$\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = \text{mex}\{0, 1, 2, 3\} = 4.$$

□

5. \mathcal{P} -positions and \mathcal{N} -positions of $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$

In this section we determine whether $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position when $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$. First, we introduce some definitions.

Definition 3. We say that a sequence of positive integers $S = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ is a *partition sequence* if $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k$. We say that the partition sequence S is *strong* if $a_k > k$.

Remark 3. The sequence $S = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ is a partition sequence in the sense that the a_i 's represent the descending terms in the partition of $N = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_k$. The partition sequence S is strong in the sense that each term a_i in the partition of $N = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_k$ is greater than the number of terms k in this partition.

Definition 4. Let $S = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ be a partition sequence. The *matrix associated with S* is the $k \times a_1$ matrix $B = [b_{i,j}]$ where $b_{i,j} = 0$ if $1 \leq i \leq k$ and $1 \leq j \leq a_1 - a_i$, and $b_{i,j} = 1$ if $1 \leq i \leq k$ and $a_1 - a_i < i \leq a_1$. We write $B = \text{mat}(S)$ and refer to B as a *partition matrix*. Let B be a partition matrix. The *partition sequence associated with B* is the sequence $S = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ where a_i is the number of 1's in row i of B , and we write $S = \text{seq}(B)$. We say that B is a *strong partition matrix* if $\text{seq}(B)$ is a strong partition sequence. See Figure 1 for an example of the strong partition matrix $[10, 8, 7, 5]$.

Remark 4. We make use of the following two observations in order to show that a game position is either a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position.

- Suppose G is a game position such that for every move G' that Player 1 can make, Player 2 can make a countermove G'' such that G'' is a \mathcal{P} -position. Then, G is a \mathcal{P} -position.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 1: The strong partition matrix $[10, 8, 7, 5]$.

- Suppose G is a game position such that Player 1 can make a move G' that is a \mathcal{P} -position. Then, G is an \mathcal{N} -position.

We first establish the conditions on a strong partition matrix $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$, where $k \in \{4, 5\}$, that determines whether it is either a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position. This serves as the base case of our argument. Then we show that, for $k \geq 6$, the strong partition matrix $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position if $a_1 \equiv a_2 \equiv k \pmod{2}$, and we show $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is an \mathcal{N} -position if $a_1 \equiv k + 1 \pmod{2}$. From these two fundamental cases, we are able to determine whether the strong partition matrix $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position depending on the parity of a_i for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$.

The following lemma provides a condition on a strong partition matrix A that allows Player 2 to remove a column with ℓ 1's after Player 1 has removed a column of ℓ 1's.

Lemma 1. *Suppose $k \geq 3$, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, and $a_\ell \equiv a_{\ell+1} \pmod{2}$ for some $1 \leq \ell \leq k - 1$. If Player 1 can remove a column with ℓ 1's from the strong partition matrix $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$, then so can Player 2. The resulting game position after these two moves is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k]$ where $b_i = a_i - 2$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq k$. Furthermore, $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_k > k$, $\text{len}(B) = \text{len}(A)$, $b_i < a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$, $b_i \leq a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq k$, and $b_i \equiv a_i \pmod{2}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k$.*

Proof. Since Player 1 can remove a column with ℓ 1's, we have $a_\ell > a_{\ell+1}$. Also, since $a_\ell \equiv a_{\ell+1} \pmod{2}$, we have $a_\ell \geq a_{\ell+1} + 2$. So, Player 2 can also remove a column with ℓ 1's. The resulting game positions is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k]$ where $b_i = a_i - 2$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq k$. Thus, $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_k > k$, $\text{len}(B) = \text{len}(A)$, $b_i < a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$, and $b_i \leq a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq k$. Also, we have $b_i = a_i - 2 \equiv a_i \pmod{2}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$, and $b_i \equiv a_i \pmod{2}$ for all $\ell < i \leq k$. □

5.1. \mathcal{P} -positions and \mathcal{N} -positions of $[a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$

We establish the conditions on (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) that determine whether $[a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position.

Theorem 7. *Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 > 4$, and let $A = [a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$. Suppose either*

- $(a_1, a_2) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{2}$ or
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3) \equiv (0, 1, 0) \pmod{2}$.

Then, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Proof. The proof is by double induction on $\text{len}(A)$ and $\text{wt}(A)$.

Case 1. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are even. Suppose Player 1 removes a column with one 1. Since $a_1 \equiv a_2 \pmod{2}$, by Lemma 1, Player 2 may also remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $[a_1 - 2, a_2, a_3, a_4]$ where $a_1 - 2$ and a_2 are even. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 2, a_2, a_3, a_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column with ℓ 1's where $2 \leq \ell \leq 4$. We let Player 2 remove row 4. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq 3$. Since $b_1 = a_1 - 1$ and $b_2 = a_2 - 1$ are odd, we have $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2, b_3]) = 0$ by Theorem 6.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ . The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq 3$. We let Player 2 remove row 3 of $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2]$ where $b_1 = a_2$ if $\ell = 1$ or $b_1 = a_1$ if $\ell > 1$. In either case, b_1 is even. By Theorem 2, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2]) = 0$.

Case 2. Assume a_1 is even, a_2 is odd, and a_3 is even. First, suppose Player 1 removes a column with one 1. The new game position is $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$. Since $a_2 \geq a_3$ and $a_2 \not\equiv a_3 \pmod{2}$, we have $a_2 > a_3$. We let Player 2 remove a column with two 1's. Next, suppose Player 1 removes a column with two 1's. The new game position is $[a_1 - 1, a_2 - 1, a_3, a_4]$. Since $a_1 - 1 \geq a_2 - 1$ and $a_1 - 1 \not\equiv a_2 - 1 \pmod{2}$, we have $a_1 - 1 > a_2 - 1$. We let Player 2 remove a column with one 1. In either case, the resulting game position is $[a_1 - 2, a_2 - 1, a_3, a_4]$ where $a_1 - 2$ and $a_2 - 1$ are even. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 2, a_2 - 1, a_3, a_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column with ℓ 1's where $3 \leq \ell \leq 4$. The new game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq 4$. We let Player 2 remove row 2. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_3, b_4]$ where $b_1 = a_1 - 1$ and $b_3 = a_3 - 1$ are odd, and $b_3 > 3$. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_3, b_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row 1. The resulting game position is $[a_2, a_3, a_4]$. We let Player 2 remove row 1 of $[a_2, a_3, a_4]$. The resulting game position is $[a_3, a_4]$ where a_3 is even. By Theorem 2, $\text{Gr}([a_3, a_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ where $2 \leq \ell \leq 4$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq 3$. We let

Player 2 remove row 3 of $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2]$ where $b_1 = a_1$ is even. By Theorem 2, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2]) = 0$. \square

Theorem 8. *Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 > 4$, and let $A = [a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$. Suppose either*

- $a_1 \equiv 1 \pmod{2}$ or
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3) \equiv (0, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

Then, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$.

Proof. Case 1. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are odd. We let Player 1 remove row 4. The resulting game position is $[a_1, a_2, a_3]$ where a_1 and a_2 are odd, and $a_3 > 4$. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3]) = 0$.

Case 2. Assume a_1 is odd and a_2 is even. Since $a_1 \geq a_2$ and $a_1 \not\equiv a_2 \pmod{2}$, $a_1 > a_2$. We let Player 1 remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$ where $a_1 - 1$ and a_2 are even. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4]) = 0$.

Case 3. Assume a_1 is even, and both a_2 and a_3 are odd. We let Player 1 remove row 1. The resulting game position is $[a_2, a_3, a_4]$ where a_2 and a_3 are odd, and $a_4 > 4$. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([a_2, a_3, a_4]) = 0$. \square

5.2. \mathcal{P} -positions and \mathcal{N} -positions of $[a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$

We now establish the conditions on $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5)$ that determine whether $[a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position.

Theorem 9. *Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 \geq a_5 > 5$, and let $A = [a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$. Suppose either*

- $(a_1, a_2) \equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$ or
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \equiv (1, 0, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

Then, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Proof. The proof is by double induction on $\text{len}(A)$ and $\text{wt}(A)$.

Case 1. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are odd. Suppose Player 1 removes a column with one 1. Since $a_1 \equiv a_2 \pmod{2}$, by Lemma 1, Player 2 may also remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $[a_1 - 2, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$ where $a_1 - 2$ and a_2 are even. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 2, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column with ℓ 1's where $2 \leq \ell \leq 5$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq 5$. We let Player 2 remove row 5 of $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ where $b_1 = a_1 - 1$ and $b_2 = a_2 - 1$ are even, and $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq b_3 \geq b_4 > 4$. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ where $1 \leq \ell \leq 2$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq 4$. We observe that $b_1 = a_2$ if $\ell = 1$, $b_1 = a_1$ if $\ell = 2$, and $b_2 = a_3$. We consider the cases b_2 is odd or even separately. If $b_2 = a_3$ is odd, we let Player 2 remove row 4 of $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$ where both b_1 and b_2 are odd. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2, b_3]) = 0$. If $b_2 = a_3$ is even, we have $b_1 > b_2$ since $b_1 \geq b_2$ and $b_1 \not\equiv b_2 \pmod{2}$. We let Player 2 remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $[b_1 - 1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ where both $b_1 - 1$ and b_2 are even. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([b_1 - 1, b_2, b_3, b_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ where $3 \leq \ell \leq 5$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq 4$. We let Player 2 remove row 4. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3]$ where $b_1 = a_1$ and $b_2 = a_2$ are odd. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2, b_3]) = 0$.

Case 2. Assume a_1, a_3 , and a_4 are odd, and a_2 is even. Suppose Player 1 removes a column with one 1. We let Player 2 remove row 5. The resulting position is $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$ where $a_1 - 1$ and a_2 are even, and $a_1 - 1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 > 4$. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column with two 1's The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq 2$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $3 \leq i \leq 5$. Since $b_1 \geq b_2$ and $b_1 \not\equiv b_2 \pmod{2}$, $b_1 > b_2$. So, we let Player 2 remove a column with one 1. The resulting position is $[b_1 - 1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]$ where $b_1 - 1 = a_1 - 2$ and $b_2 = a_2 - 1$ are odd, and $b_1 - 1 \geq b_2 \geq b_3 \geq b_4 \geq b_5 > 5$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}([b_1 - 1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column with ℓ 1's where $3 \leq \ell \leq 5$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell < i \leq 5$. We let Player 2 remove row 5 of $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4, b_5]$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$. We observe that $b_1 = a_1 - 1$ is odd, $b_2 = a_2 - 1$ is even, $b_3 = a_3 - 1$ are odd, and $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq b_3 \geq b_4 > 4$. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ where $1 \leq \ell \leq 2$. Let $\ell' \in \{1, 2\} \setminus \{\ell\}$. We let Player 2 remove row ℓ' . The resulting game position is $[a_3, a_4, a_5]$ where a_3 and a_4 are odd. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([a_3, a_4, a_5]) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ where $3 \leq \ell \leq 5$. The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq 4$. We let Player 2 remove row 2 of $[b_1, b_2, b_3, b_4]$ The resulting game position is $[b_1, b_3, b_4]$.

Since $b_3 = a_4$ if $\ell = 3$ or $b_3 = a_3$ if $\ell \in \{4, 5\}$, b_3 is odd. Thus, b_1 and b_3 are odd. By Theorem 6, $\text{Gr}([b_1, b_3, b_4]) = 0$. \square

Theorem 10. *Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 \geq a_5 > 5$, and let $A = [a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$. Suppose either*

- $a_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$ or
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \equiv (1, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ where $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

Then, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$.

Proof. Case 1. Assume both a_1 and a_2 are even. We let Player 1 remove row 5. The resulting game position is $[a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]$ where a_1 and a_2 are odd, and $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 > 5$. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4]) = 0$.

Case 2. Assume a_1 is even and a_2 is odd. Since $a_1 \geq a_2$ and $a_1 \not\equiv a_2 \pmod{2}$, $a_1 > a_2$. We let Player 1 remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $[a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$ where $a_1 - 1$ and a_2 are odd. By Theorem 9, $\text{Gr}([a_1 - 1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]) = 0$.

Case 3. Assume $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \equiv (1, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. We let Player 1 remove row 1. The resulting game position is $[a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]$ where $a_2 \geq a_3 \geq a_4 \geq a_5 > 4$. If $x = 0$, then $(a_2, a_3) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{2}$. Also, if $(x, y) = (1, 0)$, then $(a_2, a_3, a_4) \equiv (0, 1, 0) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 7, $\text{Gr}([a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5]) = 0$. \square

5.3. Some Preliminary Results on \mathcal{P} -positions and \mathcal{N} -positions

We show that when $a_i \equiv k \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2\}$, the game position $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$, where $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, is a \mathcal{P} -position.

Theorem 11. *Let $k \geq 4$. Suppose $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, $a_i \equiv k \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2\}$, and let $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.*

Proof. The proof is by double induction on $\text{len}(A)$ and $\text{wt}(A)$ of A . Let

$$\mathcal{A} = \{[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k] : k \geq 4, a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k \text{ and } a_i \equiv k \pmod{2} \text{ for all } i \in \{1, 2\}\}$$

and consider the partial order on \mathcal{A} given by

$$[b_1, b_2, \dots, b_r] \preceq [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_s] \text{ if and only if } r \leq s \text{ and } b_i \leq c_i \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq r.$$

By Theorem 7, for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $\text{len}(A) = 4$, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. By Theorem 9, for all $A \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $\text{len}(A) = 5$, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. Thus, the theorem holds for $k = 4$ and $k = 5$. This establishes the base case.

Let $k \geq 6$ and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k] \in \mathcal{A}$. Suppose $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$ for all $B \in \mathcal{A}$ such that $B \prec A$. We want to show that $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column from $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ that contains ℓ 1's. We consider the cases $\ell = 1$ and $\ell > 1$ separately. Suppose $\ell = 1$. Since $a_1 \equiv a_2 \pmod{2}$, by Lemma 1, we have $a_1 \geq a_2 + 2$. So, Player 2 can also remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k]$ where $b_1 = a_1 - 2$, and $b_i = a_i$ for all $2 \leq i \leq k$. By Lemma 1, $B \in \mathcal{A}$ and $B \prec A$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column from $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ that contains ℓ 1's where $2 \leq \ell \leq k$. We let Player 2 remove row k . Let $\ell' = \ell$ if $\ell < k$, and $\ell' = k - 1$ if $\ell = k$. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq \ell'$, and $b_i = a_i$ for all $\ell' < i \leq k - 1$. We observe that $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_{k-1} > k - 1$ and $b_i = a_i - 1 \equiv k - 1 \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2\}$. Thus, $B \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\text{len}(B) < \text{len}(A)$ and $b_i \leq a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$, $B \prec A$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ from $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq k - 1$. We consider the cases $\ell \leq 2$ and $\ell \geq 3$ separately. First, suppose $\ell \geq 3$. We let Player 2 remove row $k - 1$ of B . The resulting game position is $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{k-2}]$ where $c_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $c_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq k - 2$. Then $c_1 \geq c_2 \geq \dots \geq c_{k-2} > k - 2$, and $c_i = a_i \equiv k - 2 \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2\}$. Thus, $C \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\text{len}(C) < \text{len}(A)$ and $c_i \leq a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 2$, $C \prec A$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}(C) = 0$.

Next, suppose $\ell \leq 2$. Let $\ell' \in \{1, 2\} \setminus \{\ell\}$. We further consider the cases $a_3 \equiv k \pmod{2}$ and $a_3 \equiv k + 1 \pmod{2}$ separately. On the one hand, if $a_3 \equiv k \pmod{2}$, we let Player 2 remove row $k - 1$ of B . The resulting game position is $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{k-2}]$ where $c_1 = a_{\ell'}$ and $c_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $2 \leq i \leq k - 2$. Since $c_i \equiv k - 2 \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2\}$ and $c_1 \geq c_2 \geq \dots \geq c_{k-2} > k - 2$, $C \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\text{len}(C) < \text{len}(A)$ and $c_i \leq a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 2$, $C \prec A$. On the other hand, if $a_3 \equiv k + 1 \pmod{2}$, then $b_1 \not\equiv b_2 \pmod{2}$. Since $b_1 \geq b_2$, $b_1 \geq b_2 + 1$. So, we let Player 2 remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{k-1}]$ where $c_1 = a_{\ell'} - 1$ and $c_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $2 \leq i \leq k - 1$. We observe that $c_1 \geq c_2 \geq \dots \geq c_{k-1} > k - 1$, $c_1 = a_{\ell'} - 1 \equiv k - 1 \pmod{2}$, and $c_2 = a_3 \equiv k - 1 \pmod{2}$. Thus, $C \in \mathcal{A}$. Since $\text{len}(C) < \text{len}(A)$ and $c_i \leq a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$, $C \prec A$. In either case, we have $\text{Gr}(C) = 0$ by the inductive hypothesis. This completes the proof. \square

The next result provides a condition on (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) to ensure that the game

position $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is an \mathcal{N} -position.

Theorem 12. *Let $k \geq 5$. Suppose $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, $a_1 \equiv k + 1 \pmod{2}$, and let $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$.*

Proof. We consider the cases $a_2 \equiv k \pmod{2}$ and $a_2 \equiv k + 1 \pmod{2}$ separately. First, suppose $a_2 \equiv k \pmod{2}$. Since $a_1 \geq a_2$ and $a_1 \not\equiv a_2 \pmod{2}$, $a_1 \geq a_2 + 1$. So, we let Player 1 remove a column with one 1. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k]$ where $b_1 = a_1 - 1$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $2 \leq i \leq k$. Then $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_k > k$, $b_1 = a_1 - 1 \equiv k \pmod{2}$, and $b_2 = a_2 \equiv k \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$.

Next, suppose $a_2 \equiv k + 1 \pmod{2}$. We let Player 1 remove row k . The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$. Then $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_{k-1} > k - 1$, and $b_i = a_i \equiv k - 1 \pmod{2}$ for all $i \in \{1, 2\}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. \square

5.4. The Main Result

We introduce the following notation in order to state when $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position.

Notation 1. Suppose (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k) is a sequence of 0's and 1's. We let $(b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k)^n$ represent the concatenation of n copies of (b_1, b_2, \dots, b_k) . For example, $(1, 0)^3 = (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 0)$.

We state the conditions that are needed on the strong partition sequence $S = (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k)$ in order to determine whether the strong partition matrix $\text{mat}(S)$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position. Theorems 13 and 14 provide the conditions to ensure that $\text{mat}(S)$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position, respectively, when k is even, and Theorems 15 and 16 provide the conditions to ensure that $\text{mat}(S)$ is a \mathcal{P} -position or an \mathcal{N} -position, respectively, when k is odd.

Theorem 13. *Let $k = 2p \geq 4$ be even, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ if and only if either*

- $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((0, 1)^q, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 3$
or
- $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq k - 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-2}, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

Theorem 14. *Let $k = 2p \geq 4$ be even, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$ if and only if $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^q, 1) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 1$.*

Theorem 15. *Let $k = 2p + 1$ be odd, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ if and only if $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((1, 0)^q, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 1$.*

Theorem 16. *Let $k = 2p + 1$ be odd, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k$, and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$ if and only if either*

- $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 1) \equiv ((1, 0)^q, 0) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 2$ or
- $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq k - 1) \equiv ((1, 0)^{p-1}, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

In order to establish Theorems 13, 14, 15, and 16, we first demonstrate that Theorem 13 is equivalent to Theorem 14 when k is even, and Theorem 15 is equivalent to Theorem 16 when k is odd. Next, we establish the necessity of Theorems 13, 14, 15, and 16. These arguments establish the claims made in Theorems 13, 14, 15, and 16. Then, we consider the special case $k = 7$ as an example.

Lemma 2. *When $k \geq 4$ is even, Theorem 13 is equivalent to Theorem 14. Similarly, when $k \geq 5$ is odd, Theorem 15 is equivalent to Theorem 16.*

Proof. We demonstrate that when $k \geq 4$ is even, Theorem 13 is equivalent to Theorem 14. The proof that Theorem 15 is equivalent to Theorem 16 when k is odd is similar, and we leave the proof of that case to the reader.

Let $k = 2p \geq 4$ be even. The proof will be by backwards induction on $0 \leq q \leq p - 2$. We show that, for each integer q such that $0 \leq q \leq p - 2$, among the $2^{2p-2q-1}$ choices of parity of a_i where $2q + 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 1$, there are

$$(2^2 - 1) + 2^3 + 2^5 + \dots + 2^{2p-2q-2} = \frac{1}{3}(2^{2p-2q-1} + 1)$$

choices of parity for which $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position and

$$1 + 2^2 + 2^4 + \dots + 2^{2p-2q-2} = \frac{1}{3}(2^{2p-2q} - 1)$$

complementary choices of parity for which $[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ is an \mathcal{N} -position.

We let $S = (a_i : 1 \leq i \leq k)$, $A = \text{mat}(S)$, and $q = p - 2$. By Theorem 13, if $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-2}, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$, then $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. By Theorem 14, if $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-2}, 1) \pmod{2}$ or $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 3) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-3}, 1) \pmod{2}$, then $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. Thus, among the $2^3 = 2^{2p-2q-1}$ choices of parity of a_i where $2q + 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 1$, $2^2 - 1 = \frac{1}{3}(2^3 + 1)$ choices of parity yield $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ and $2^0 + 2^2 = \frac{1}{3}(2^4 - 1)$ complementary choices of parity yield $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. This establishes the base case.

Suppose that, for some integer $1 \leq q \leq p - 2$, among the $2^{2p-2q-1}$ choices of parity of a_i where $2q + 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 1$,

$$(2^2 - 1) + 2^3 + 2^5 + \dots + 2^{2p-2q-3} = \frac{1}{3}(2^{2p-2q-1} + 1)$$

choices of parity yield $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ and

$$2^0 + 2^2 + 2^4 + \dots + 2^{2p-2q-2} = \frac{1}{3}(2^{2p-2q} - 1)$$

complementary choices of parity yield $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. By Theorem 13, if $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q) \equiv ((0, 1)^{q-1}, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$, then $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. By Theorem 14, if $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q - 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^{q-1}, 1) \pmod{2}$, then $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. Thus, among the $2^{2p-2(q-1)-1}$ choices of parity of a_i where $2(q - 1) + 1 \leq i \leq 2p - 1$,

$$(2^2 - 1) + 2^3 + 2^5 + \dots + 2^{2p-2(q-1)-3} = \frac{1}{3}(2^{2p-2(q-1)-1} + 1)$$

choices of parity yield $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ and

$$2^0 + 2^2 + 2^4 + \dots + 2^{2p-2(q-1)-2} = \frac{1}{3}(2^{2p-2(q-1)} - 1)$$

complementary choices of parity yield $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. This completes the proof. \square

Remark 5. We let $\langle x \rangle$ denote the *nearest integer function* defined by $\langle x \rangle \in \mathbb{Z}$ such that $x - \frac{1}{2} < \langle x \rangle \leq x + \frac{1}{2}$. Let $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ be a strong partition matrix. For $k \geq 4$, among the 2^{k-1} choices of parity of a_i where $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$, there are $\langle \frac{1}{3} 2^{k-1} \rangle$ choices of parity that yield $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ and $\langle \frac{1}{3} 2^k \rangle$ complementary choices of parity that yield $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$.

We provide the proofs of Theorems 13, 14, 15, and 16.

Proof of necessity of Theorems 13 and 15. The proof is by double induction on the length of A and the game weight of A . Let

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{E} &= \{[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k] : k = 2p \geq 4 \text{ is even, } a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k, \text{ and either} \\ &\quad (a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((0, 1)^q, 0, 0) \pmod{2} \text{ for some integer } 0 \leq q \leq p - 3, \text{ or} \\ &\quad (a_i : 1 \leq i \leq k - 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-2}, 0, x, y) \pmod{2} \text{ and } (x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}\}, \\ \mathcal{O} &= \{[a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k] : k \geq 5 \text{ is odd, } a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_k > k, \text{ and} \\ &\quad (a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((1, 0)^q, 1, 1) \pmod{2} \text{ for some integer } 0 \leq q \leq p - 1\}, \\ \mathcal{C} &= \mathcal{E} \cup \mathcal{O}, \end{aligned}$$

and consider the partial order on \mathcal{C} given by

$$\begin{aligned} [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_r] \preceq [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_s] \text{ if and only if} \\ r \leq s \text{ and } b_i \leq c_i \text{ for all } 1 \leq i \leq r. \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem 7, for all $A \in \mathcal{C}$ such that $\text{len}(A) = 4$, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. By Theorem 9, for all $A \in \mathcal{C}$ such that $\text{len}(A) = 5$, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. Thus, the theorem holds for $k = 4$ and $k = 5$. This establishes the base case.

Let $k \geq 6$ and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k] \in \mathcal{C}$. Suppose for all $B \in \mathcal{C}$ such that $B \prec A$, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. We want to show that $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. We consider the cases k is even and k is odd separately.

Suppose k is even. First, suppose $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((0, 1)^q, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 3$. If $q = 0$, then $(a_1, a_2) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. So, we may assume $q \geq 1$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column from $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ that contains one 1. We let Player 2 remove row k of A . The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_1 = a_1 - 1$ and $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 < i \leq k - 1$. We observe that $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_{k-1} > k - 1$, $\text{len}(B) = k - 1$ is odd, and $(b_1, b_2) \equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column from $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ that contains two 1's. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_i - 1$ for all $1 \leq i \leq 2$, and $b_i = a_i$ for all $2 < i \leq k$. Since b_1 is odd, b_2 is even, and $b_1 \geq b_2$, we have $b_1 \geq b_2 + 1$. So, we let Player 2 remove a column that contains one 1. The resulting game position is $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_k]$ where $c_1 = a_1 - 2$, $c_2 = a_2 - 1$, and $c_i = a_i$ for all $3 \leq i \leq k$. We observe that $c_1 \geq c_2 \geq \dots \geq c_k > k$, $\text{len}(C) = k$ is even, and $(c_1, c_2) \equiv (0, 0) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(C) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes a column from $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ that contains ℓ 1's such that $3 \leq \ell \leq k$. We let Player 2 remove row 2 of A . The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_1 = a_1 - 1$, $b_i = a_{i+1} - 1$ for all $2 \leq i < \ell$, and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq k - 1$. We observe that $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_{k-1} > k - 1$, $\text{len}(B) = k - 1$ is odd, and $(b_1, b_2) \equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

If Player 1 removes row 1 of $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$, we let Player 2 remove row 2 of A . If Player 1 removes row 2 of A , we let Player 2 remove row 1 of A . Then the resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-2}]$ where $b_i = a_{i+2}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 2$. Since $b_1 \geq b_2 \geq \dots \geq b_{k-2} > k - 2$, $\text{len}(B) = k - 2$ is even, and $(b_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q) \equiv ((0, 1)^{q-1}, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$, we have $B \in \mathcal{C}$. Since $\text{len}(B) < \text{len}(A)$ and $b_i \leq a_i$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 2$, we have $B \prec A$. By the inductive hypothesis, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ of $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ where $3 \leq \ell \leq k$. The resulting position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_i$ for all $1 \leq i < \ell$ and $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq k - 1$. Since b_1 is even, b_2 is odd, and $b_1 \geq b_2$, we have $b_1 \geq b_2 + 1$. So, we let Player 2 remove a column with one 1. The resulting position is $C = [c_1, c_2, \dots, c_{k-1}]$ where $c_1 = a_1 - 1$, $c_i = a_i$ for all $2 \leq i < \ell$ and $c_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $\ell \leq i \leq k - 1$. We observe that $c_1 \geq c_2 \geq \dots \geq c_{k-1} > k - 1$, $\text{len}(C) = k - 1$ is odd, and $(c_1, c_2) \equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 11, $\text{Gr}(C) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$.

Suppose k is even and $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq k - 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-2}, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ where $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. Suppose Player 1 removes a column with ℓ 1's of $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ where $1 \leq \ell \leq k$. An argument similar to that in paragraphs 4, 5, and 6 of this proof shows that $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. We leave the details to the reader.

Suppose Player 1 removes row ℓ of $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k]$ where $1 \leq \ell \leq k$. An argument as above shows that $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$. We leave the details to the reader.

Suppose k is odd and $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((1, 0)^q, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 1$. The proof is similar to the proof that $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ when k is even and $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 2) \equiv ((0, 1)^q, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 3$. We leave the details to the reader. \square

Proof of necessity of Theorem 14. Let $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 1) \equiv ((0, 1)^q, 1) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 1$. First, suppose $q = 0$. Then, by Theorem 12, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. Next, suppose $q \geq 1$. We let Player 1 remove row 1. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$. Then $(b_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q) \equiv ((1, 0)^{q-1}, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 15, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. \square

Proof of necessity of Theorem 16. Let $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q + 1) \equiv ((1, 0)^q, 0) \pmod{2}$ for some integer $0 \leq q \leq p - 2$. First, suppose $q = 0$. Then, by Theorem 12, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. Next, suppose $q \geq 1$. We let Player 1 remove row 1. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$. Then $(b_i : 1 \leq i \leq 2q) \equiv ((0, 1)^{q-1}, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 13, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$.

Let $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq k - 1) \equiv ((1, 0)^{p-1}, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. We let Player 1 remove row 1. The resulting game position is $B = [b_1, b_2, \dots, b_{k-1}]$ where $b_i = a_{i+1}$ for all $1 \leq i \leq k - 1$. Then, $(b_i : 1 \leq i \leq k - 2) \equiv ((0, 1)^{p-2}, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$. By Theorem 13, $\text{Gr}(B) = 0$. Thus, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$. \square

Example 1. We consider the special case $k = 7$. Then, Theorems 15 and 16 specialize to the following two propositions.

Proposition 2. Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_7 > 7$ and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_7]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) = 0$ if and only if either

- $(a_1, a_2) \equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$,
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \equiv (1, 0, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$, or
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \equiv (1, 0, 1, 0, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

Proposition 3. Let $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq \dots \geq a_7 > 7$ and $A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_7]$. Then, $\text{Gr}(A) \neq 0$ if and only if either

- $a_1 \equiv 0 \pmod{2}$,
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3) \equiv (1, 0, 0) \pmod{2}$, or
- $(a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4, a_5, a_6) \equiv (1, 0, 1, 0, x, y) \pmod{2}$ and $(x, y) \not\equiv (1, 1) \pmod{2}$.

$$\begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Figure 2: The strong partition matrix $A = [19, 18, 15, 14, 11, 9, 8]$ is a \mathcal{P} -position.

Example 2. We consider the strong partition matrix $A = [19, 18, 15, 14, 11, 9, 8]$ depicted in Figure 2. Then, $\text{seq}(A) = (a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 7) = (19, 18, 15, 14, 11, 9, 8)$. Since $(a_i : 1 \leq i \leq 6) \equiv ((1, 0)^2, 1, 1) \pmod{2}$, A is a \mathcal{P} -position by Proposition 2.

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